

IMPACT OF BUDGET MANAGEMENT REFORM ON THE PERFORMANCE OF GOVERNMENT ENTITIES IN NIGERIA

By

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ABSTRACT

Budget management plays a pivotal role in the effective functioning of government entities. The need for reform arises from the challenges faced by traditional budgeting systems, and the Nigerian government's commitment to good governance and economic development. The main objective of this study therefore, was to investigate the impact of budget management reform (BMR) on the performance of government entities' in Nigeria. The study applied mixed method approach with a sample size of 306. Quantitative data was analysed using Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model while qualitative data was analysed with thematic/NVIVO. Finding indicates that for every increase on the impact of Budget Management Reform there was an increment on the overall performance of government entities as a result of the effects on the reduction on budget infraction level in Nigeria. In line with the findings from this study,

it was concluded that positive relation exist between budget management reform and performance of government entities in Nigeria. The study therefore, recommends that government should universally implement budget management policies so as to curb practices that encourage infractions on budget implementations in Nigeria.

Key words; *Financial planning, allocation, oversight within government, organizational settings.*

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1. INTRODUCTION.

Budget management reform in Nigeria is a critical issue that has attracted significant attention from scholars and policymakers in recent years. Nigeria's budget management system has undergone several reforms aimed at improving transparency, accountability, and effectiveness in the use of public funds (Oji, Eze & Irohibe, 2021). These reforms include the introduction of the Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) and the Fiscal Responsibility Act (FRA) in 2007. The MTEF was designed to improve the linkage between planning and budgeting, while the FRA was aimed at promoting prudent management of public resources (Olumuyiwa, 2017). Prior to gaining independence from British colonial rule in 1960, Nigeria's budget management was largely centralized and under British control. The colonial government controlled the finances, and there was limited fiscal autonomy for Nigeria (Falokun, 2013). After gaining independence, Nigeria developed its own budgeting and financial management system. During this period, the country experienced significant economic growth fueled by oil revenue. The budgeting process was however, relatively centralized and characterized by a heavy reliance on oil revenue (Ikejiofor, 2003).

In response to economic challenges, Nigeria implemented Structural Adjustment Programs (SAPs) in the 1980s and 1990s, which aimed to reform public financial management and reduce government expenditure. These programs led to significant changes in budget management practices (Olowa, 2016). Nigeria has however, undergone various budget reforms in the 21st century. Notable reforms include the introduction of the Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) and the Fiscal Responsibility Act (FRA) in 2007. These reforms aimed to enhance transparency, accountability, and fiscal discipline in budget management (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2007).

Research Objectives

The main objective of the study is to investigate the impact of Budget Management Reform on the performance of government entities' in Nigeria;

Scope of the Study

The geographical scope of this study is Nigeria Government Entities' with specific focus on 12 (Twelve) Entities' comprises of 7 (seven) entities' initially commissioned as "PILOT entities' under phase 1 (one) of the Public Sector Financial Management Reforms initiatives of federal government in Nigeria as well as 5 (Five) other critical stakeholders and participants in the reforms agenda (Torough, 2011; Salawu 2012).

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Budget Management Reforms (BMRs)

Budgeting is a managerial process involving the planning, preparation, and control of budgets, guiding future-oriented actions rather than merely reporting (Kelly & Tobi, 2020; Ianna, 2018). It creates a spending plan to balance an entity's income and expenses, supporting financial readiness (Prachi, 2015). Unlike forecasting, which predicts likely future conditions, budgeting emphasizes detailed planning and actionable goals, acting as a control tool for managing resources (Matt, 2000; Adetayo, 2017; Mwaura, 2013).

In organizations, budgeting serves short-term financial goals and supports long-term objectives, breaking down income, expenditures, savings, and investments, often on a monthly basis (Malgwi & Unegbu, 2012). The budgeting process typically includes estimating income, expenses, and finalizing the budget, adjusting for potential cost-of-living changes (Kalimalwendo, 2005). For the public sector, frameworks like the Medium Term Sector Strategy (MTSS) and its revenue and expenditure components (MTRF and MTEF) enable planning and community engagement, which is essential for effectively addressing government programs and policies.

Financial Performance (FP)

Financial performance assesses how effectively a firm utilizes assets to generate revenue and overall financial health over time. This metric allows comparisons within industries or sectors. Common measures include revenue, operating income, cash flow, unit sales, productivity, and profit, as well as financial ratios like return on assets (Bessler, 2008; Loof, Hans & Heshmati, 2002; Business Dictionary, 2011).

From an accounting perspective, financial statements summarize a firm's financial and operational data annually, serving as diagnostic tools for management. Performance measurement often focuses on financial ratios—such as profitability, asset utilization, leverage, and liquidity ratios—which help assess a firm's capacity to maximize shareholder wealth and

profitability (Farah, Farrukh & Faizan, 2016). These ratios have shown varied impacts on financial outcomes, with return on investment (ROI) as a common indicator.

In the public sector, financial performance analysis often relies on profitability ratios and statements of financial performance (Profit and Loss Account) to understand resource efficiency and the generation of economic surplus, central to financial management (Mara & Nicoleta, 2019).

Related Theoretical

The impact of budget management reforms on Nigerian government entities is analyzed using the Principal-Agent Theory, which examines the relationship between the government (principal) and public officials or agencies (agents). This theory, formalized by Jensen and Meckling in 1976, highlights issues arising from information asymmetry and goal misalignment between principals and agents.

In Nigeria, the government often lacks complete information on the performance of agencies, which can lead to inefficiencies and misaligned goals, such as prioritizing agency objectives over public service goals (Ezeani & Nnadi, 2014; Oyetunji & Adejuwon, 2018). Budget reforms like performance-based budgeting aim to address these issues by improving monitoring, control, and accountability through performance indicators, financial reporting, and incentive structures (Ololube, 2013). Reforms also aim to reduce agency costs—expenses related to monitoring and controlling agents—by enhancing transparency (Jibrin & Khan, 2017).

Despite its utility, the theory faces criticism for oversimplifying human behavior, assuming rationality, and downplaying non-monetary incentives and organizational culture. Nonetheless, in Nigeria's context, marked by challenges in resource allocation and accountability, the Principal-Agent Theory remains a useful framework for understanding and guiding budget reforms to improve government performance, efficiency, and service delivery (Pfeffer, 1992; Hoskisson & Turk, 1990; Eisenhardt, 1989).

Empirical Discourse

Historically, public budgeting primarily focused on controlling public revenue and expenditure. However, mid-20th century economic shifts, influenced by Keynesian ideas, expanded the budget's role, positioning it as a tool for political, economic, and administrative management in the public sector. This broadened perspective led to interdisciplinary analysis of budgeting.

In a review of European public budgeting research, Anessi-Pessina, Barbera, Sicilia, and Steccolini (2016) identified three main research approaches: (i) qualitative empirical research (using non-standardized data to analyze text and images), (ii) quantitative empirical research (using standardized data for statistical analysis), and (iii) normative research (prescribing ideal budgetary features). Empirical studies were further categorized into descriptive and exploratory research (to illustrate or explore phenomena) and explanatory research (to understand causes and conditions of events).

The analysis in international academic journals on public-sector budgeting largely focuses on public administration, management, and public-sector accounting, often viewing budgeting as part of broader reform processes. This perspective, while sacrificing some detail, has enabled a cumulative understanding of reform in the Public Sector, refining theories and methods over time.

In a related study, Tatiana, Oleg, Alla, Veronica, and Denis (2016) proposed methods to align budgeting mechanisms with strategic development goals for companies in the Netherlands. Their research employed various theoretical, diagnostic, empirical, and statistical methods to expand budgeting as a type of financial planning. They introduced a budgeting technique based on asset turnover, sales profitability, and return on assets to measure company efficiency. These findings can aid in improving financial management and creating effective budgeting mechanisms in both development companies and Public Sector Entities.

Ajibolade and Oboh (2017) conducted an empirical review of Nigeria's budgeting and public funds management (PSFM) practices, revealing significant issues in accountability, transparency, and fiscal effectiveness. They found that Nigeria's annual budgeting process is flawed, failing to meet its fiscal goals, and that the nation's economic development is not proportionate to its government spending. This study also touches on the origins of Nigeria's financial planning and budgeting reform efforts.

Similarly, Darge (2018) examined the budget and budgetary control systems in public organizations in Ethiopia's East Wollega Zone. The study focused on three selected Finance and Economic Development Offices, surveying 150 employees. Using SPSS for analysis, it identified low levels of budget planning, monitoring, control, and participative budgeting, all of which were linked to reduced organizational effectiveness. These findings highlight challenges in budget management that impact public sector efficiency in both Nigeria and Ethiopia.

Nwokenkwo (2019) evaluated the effects of budgeting and budgetary control on construction project delivery in Nigeria, specifically examining the budgeting practices of clients, consultants, and contractors from project inception to completion. Using a structured survey with seventy respondents selected via stratified random sampling, the study found that poor budgetary control often led to time and cost overruns. However, since this study focused on the private sector, comparing its findings with public sector performance poses challenges.

Chen (2019) conducted a historical review of China's Budget Management System from 1949 to 2019. The study highlighted the system's evolution from a centralized, planned-economy model to a modern, transparent, and standardized budgeting framework, reflecting China's shift toward a market economy. While the reform achieved significant progress, Chen noted that China's current budgetary system still has gaps relative to the demands of modern governance, indicating areas for future improvement.

David and Ron (2020) analyzed the UK's budgetary response to COVID-19, examining how the pandemic affected public sector financial management. Using data from official sources on government receipts and expenditures, the study highlighted substantial fiscal shifts: a 12% drop in government receipts and a 36% rise in expenditures from April to June 2020, compared to the prior year. Government debt surged to £1,984 billion (99.6% of GDP), the highest since 1961, with projections indicating a potential deficit of £322 billion, raising debt further to £2,205 billion (104.1% of GDP).

The study noted that the UK's fiscal sustainability is at risk, with the pandemic stressing the importance of prompt financial reporting. Practical implications show an emphasis on statistical accounting and budgeting for quick data reporting and international comparability, marginalizing financial reporting temporarily. Social implications suggest that rising debt, coupled with potential interest rate hikes, could lead to austerity and increased centralization of fiscal power. This research offers an early structured analysis of COVID-19's impact on UK government finances, emphasizing both the immediate fiscal strain and long-term sustainability concerns.

Raya and Maria (2021) investigated the impact of budgetary control on the financial performance of Oman Telecommunications Company, focusing on the effectiveness of various budgetary control techniques and the role of top management support. Using questionnaires, interviews, and statistical analysis (including regression analysis and correlation), the study found a positive relationship between budgetary control and financial performance. The study

highlighted the effectiveness of variance analysis and accounting responsibility as key techniques used by the company, and it underscored the importance of management support in successful budget control.

Ijaiya, Sanni, Olabisi, and Dolapo (2021) examined budget management and control challenges in the Nigerian public sector, specifically in Kwara State’s Ministry of Finance. Using questionnaires distributed to 64 respondents, the study identified issues such as non-compliance with regulations and unrealistic budget estimations. Despite these challenges, the study found that mechanisms for budget efficiency and effectiveness, tested through Chi-square and One Sample t-tests, were largely sound.

3 METHODOLOGY

Research Design.

This study employed a mixed-methods approach using a convergent parallel design, where both structured questionnaires (quantitative) and semi-structured interviews (qualitative) were used to collect primary data. This approach allowed the researcher to interact directly with respondents, gathering detailed insights into their perceptions, opinions, and experiences on the topic (Creswell, 2013; David, 2014).

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A sample size of 306 was determined for the quantitative aspect using Krejcie & Morgan's (1970) sample size table, while purposive sampling was used to select 3 respondents for the qualitative interviews, based on the guidelines of Stephen, Jenn, and Ann (2005). These 3 key respondents, who were directly involved with the Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS) implementation, were selected using the researcher’s experience and judgment to ensure that the responses provided would be fact-based and relevant to the study of IFMIS implementation and the performance of government entities in Nigeria (Kombo & Tromp, 2009).

Model Specification

The study adapted the model of Effiong et al (2017) to establish the relationship between TSA, IPPIS, IFMIS and fraud management in Public Sector (FMPS) in Nigeria with linear regression model stated as:-

$$FMPS = b_0 + b_1TSA + b_2IPPIS + b_3IFMIS + \mu \dots \dots \dots 3.1.$$

Where: FMPS = Fraud management in Public Sector

TSA = Treasury Single Account

IPPIS = Integrated Personnel & Payroll Information System

IFMS = Integrated Financial Management Information System

μ = Error Term

The model specified in equation (3.1) above, was modified in order to achieve the objectives of this study as stated below:

$$GEP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BMR_i + \mu \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

Where:

GEP = Government Entity Performance

BMR = Budget Management Reform

Decision Rule

If the observed probability is greater than preferred level of significance (0.05), Null Hypothesis is accepted, but if otherwise, reject null hypothesis.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

Financial Performance: The respondents’ views on financial performance are shown in Table 4.1 based on the questions from FP1 to FP7 (that is, research question one to seven). The mean score for Financial Performance ranges from 3.28 to 4.14, with standard deviations of 0.949 and 1.306, respectively.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics for Financial Performance

Items	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
FP1	306	1	5	3.77	1.121
FP2	306	1	5	3.28	1.306
FP3	306	1	5	3.87	1.275
FP4	306	1	5	3.88	1.099
FP5	306	1	5	4.01	1.071
FP6	306	1	5	3.86	1.121
FP7	306	1	5	4.14	0.949

Source: Author’s Computation, 2024

Table 1 shows the mean score between 3.28 and 4.14, with standard deviations of 0.949 and 1.306. This implies that government entities’ have opportunities to request for sufficient budget appropriation, funds release and cash-backings as well as efficient budget implementation using the fiscal strategic guidelines is capable of enhancing capacity utilisation of funds.

Non-Financial Performance: The respondents’ views on non-financial performance are shown in Table 4.2 based on questions from NFP1 to NFP6. The mean score ranges from 4.05 to 4.28, with standard deviations between 0.806 and 0.967, respectively.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics for Non-Financial Performance

Items	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
NFP1	306	1	5	4.28	0.806
NFP2	306	1	5	4.13	0.928
NFP3	306	1	5	4.17	0.860
NFP4	306	1	5	4.16	0.879
NFP5	306	1	5	4.16	0.909
NFP6	306	1	5	4.05	0.967

Source: Author’s Computation, 2024

Table 2 shows the mean score from 4.05 to 4.28, with standard deviations between 0.806 and 0.967 on non-financial performance which indicates as per NFP1 to NFP6 that government entities’ have potentials for an overall strategy to achieve entities’ objectives, motivated enhanced staff productivity as well as quality service delivery to citizenry.

Descriptive Statistics of Budget Management Reform (BMR): The respondents’ views on budget management reform are shown in Table 4.3 based on questions from BMR1 to BMR14. The mean score ranges from 4.24 to 4.46, with standard deviations between 0.578 and 0.895, respectively.

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics for Budget Management Reform

Items	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
BMR1	306	1	5	4.24	0.895
BMR2	306	1	5	4.42	0.698
BMR3	306	1	5	4.25	0.644
BMR4	306	1	5	4.38	0.693
BMR5	306	1	5	4.22	0.688
BMR6	306	1	5	4.30	0.810
BMR7	306	1	5	4.36	0.773
BMR8	306	1	5	4.32	0.734
BMR9	306	1	5	4.34	0.815

BMR10	306	1	5	4.28	0.638
BMR11	306	1	5	4.45	0.637
BMR12	306	1	5	4.32	0.644
BMR13	306	1	5	4.23	0.821
BMR14	306	1	5	4.46	0.578

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

The result of the analysis indicates that government entities' need to adhere to the provision of fiscal responsibility Act, participatory budget practices with stakeholders and linkage to National Fiscal Strategies is high at the mean score of 4.46, with standard deviations of 0.895.

Normality Test

This test is typically used to determine whether the data collected for the study is normally distributed; thus, in this regard, the researcher used Skewness and Kurtosis statistics. As presented in table 4.4, all Skewness and Kurtosis values for each research variables ranges between -3.351 to +1.648 for skewness and +1.156 to +2.748 for kurtosis are within Kline's (1998) recommended range of -3 to +3. The scores on each variable are assumed to be normally distributed in many parametric statistics (in example, follow the shape of the normal curve). The findings in this investigation as shown in Table 4.9 indicates that results are fairly normally distributed.

Table 4 Test of Normality

	N	Skewness	Kurtosis
Budget Management Reform	306	1.648	1.927
Financial Performance	306	-1.217	1.156
Non-Financial Performance	306	-1.454	2.263

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Structural Model: The second part of the assessment is the structural model, applied when the measurement model assessment is satisfactory. As described by Hair et al. (2016), five key criteria form the assessment for the structural model in PLS-SEM. These include examining the collinearity, coefficient of determination (R^2), effect sizes (f^2), the relevance of the path coefficients, the statistical significance, and the predictive relevance (Q^2 and PLS predict). Hair et al. (2016) recommended that it is essential to test for collinearity before proceeding with other structural relationship assessments. The Variance Inflation Factors

(VIF) was used to assess multicollinearity among the variables, and the result is shown in table 5. Therefore, it is established that collinearity issues do not exist among the constructs as all the values of the VIF are below the threshold of 3.3 (Hair et al., 2016).

Table 5 Result of the Collinearity Assessment (Variance Inflation Factor)

Constructs	Financial Performance	Non-Financial Performance
Budget Management Reforms	1.525	1.525

Author's computation, 2024

Path Coefficients Results for Model 1 (M1)

Model M1 is predicated upon the assumption that the budget management reform (BMR) does not predict the performance of government entities' in Nigeria. This assumption forms the basis for hypothesis H₀₁ for the study. The hypothesis was tested using BMR role in budget management) as predictor variables and the government Entities performance (financial and non-financial performance) as the dependent variable in the PLS-SEM analysis. Figure 1 showed that BMR predicts FP and NFP The result as displayed in table 6 and Figure 4.3 showed that all relationships were significant. Specifically, BMR has a greater influence on non-financial performance ($\beta = 0.559$, $p < 0.001$). Also, BMR has a significant and positive influence on financial performance ($\beta = 0.469$, $p < 0.001$). The results imply that BMR plays greater roles in the management of government Entities budget management and performance in the area of resource allocations and expenditure control and management which is in tune with the philosophy of theory of the budget.

Table 6 Budget Management Reform (BMR); Model 1 (M1) Hypothesis Testing

	β	Std Error	T-Value	P Values	Confidence Interval	
					5.00%	95.00%
BMR -> FP	0.469	0.093	5.078	0.000	0.255	0.586
BMR -> NFP	0.559	0.113	4.952	0.000	0.287	0.693

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Figure 1 Structural Model for Model 1 (M1)

Source; Author's Conceptualisation, 2024

The analysis in figure 4.1 above display the authenticity of the result of the path coefficient of the structural model on table 6. The Beta (β) and P Value (P) are values on the lines while the Confidence Interval (CI) are the values on the circles. The figures indicated that all the tests were conducted through Smart PLS.

Qualitative Analysis

Theme: Budget Management Reform and Entities' Performance

Budget management reform is a theme that occurred through the interview. Most of the respondents agree that BMR is an effective reform that has been able to control the spending of the MDAs as well as minimize risks of budget non-performance. More so, the respondents underscored the importance of the reform process to expedite actions effectively and efficiently on budget preparations with minimal errors, limits excessive spending of the MDAs as well as control expenditures; these factors emerged as the sub-themes under BMR. Some of the respondents, such as respondent 2 agreed that BMR has reinforced the ability of the government to cut excessive spending and control revenue. Respondent 2 also agreed with the earlier position of respondent 1, and further added that BMR has reduced the cost of budgeting processes in the country and that BMR has also brought a centralized and uniform mode of budget preparation among the different MDAs, which is in contrast with previous mode of preparation. Respondent 3 agreed that 'I.'

Integrated Findings

The integration of both quantitative and qualitative findings in this study highlighted the comprehensive impact of Budget Management Reform (BMR) on the performance of government entities in Nigeria. The study revealed that BMR positively influenced key areas such as revenue stability, expenditure management, and fiscal discipline, contributing to improved performance indicators and more efficient resource allocation.

Overall, the results suggest that a well-designed and effectively managed BMR can significantly enhance the performance of government entities. By fostering fiscal discipline and promoting prudent financial management, BMR presents a promising approach to addressing fiscal challenges and supporting sustainable socio-economic development in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study offer valuable insights into the impact of Budget Management Reform (BMR) on the performance of government entities in Nigeria. Both the quantitative analysis of financial data and the qualitative feedback from key stakeholders provide a comprehensive understanding of the BMR's effectiveness in achieving its objectives.

The quantitative results demonstrated a positive correlation between BMR implementation and improvements in government entity performance indicators. Entities that adhered to the Medium-Term Sector Strategy (MTSS) guidelines showed increased efficiency and effectiveness, emphasizing the importance of evidence-based policymaking. The study suggests that BMR can be a key tool for improving public service delivery outcomes.

Additionally, the study highlighted that BMR strengthened fiscal discipline in government entities through the "envelope style" budgeting approach, which set strong revenue targets and expenditure ceilings. The Medium-Term Revenue Framework (MTRF) fostered a more disciplined approach to budgeting and financial management, leading to reduced budget overruns and improved adherence to fiscal rules. These findings underscore the role of BMR in enhancing fiscal governance, mitigating fiscal risks, and promoting sustainable fiscal policies that contribute to macroeconomic stability in Nigeria.

5. Conclusion

This study examines the impact of Budget Management reform on the performance of government entities in Nigeria. The primary objective was to investigate how budget management reforms affect government performance. A mixed-method approach (quantitative and qualitative) was used to gather data. A structured questionnaire collected

quantitative data, which was analyzed using the model by Baid (2017) and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Qualitative data were gathered through interviews with senior officers in selected government entities and analyzed using narrative and thematic analysis with NVIVO.

The findings indicate that as the impact of Budget Management reform increases, there is a corresponding improvement in the performance of government entities, particularly in reducing budget infractions. The study concludes that a positive relationship exists between budget management reform and government performance in Nigeria. It recommends that the government should implement budget management policies universally to reduce infractions in budget implementation.

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THE EFFECT OF GOVERNMENT POLICIES ON PROPERTY TAX COMPLIANCE AMONG NIGERIAN LANDOWNERS

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